

INHERITANCE AND VARIABILITY OF THE PLANT HEIGHT TRAIT IN CHINESE-UZBEK COTTON GERMPLASM SAMPLES (UNDER A 0:1:0 IRRIGATION REGIME)

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the inheritance, variability, and formation of plant height (main stem height) in Chinese-Uzbek cotton germplasm accessions and F_2 hybrid populations under a 0:1:0 irrigation regime. Statistical and mathematical analyses were used to evaluate the average growth rate, the range of population variability, and the stability of the trait in varieties and hybrids. The results demonstrated a strong heterosis effect in tall hybrids with vigorous vegetative growth, while short-statured varieties exhibited the presence of growth-restricting genes. Based on the coefficient of variation ($V\%$), the level of genetic stability of the populations was determined, and promising donors, stable varieties, and highly variable F_2 populations were identified for breeding purposes. The findings have significant scientific and practical importance for developing high-yielding, mechanization-friendly cotton cultivars with tall or compact growth habits.

Introduction. Plant height is one of the most important morphobiological traits in cotton breeding, as it directly influences several economically significant characteristics such as vegetative growth vigor, the number of fruiting branches, productivity level, lodging resistance, adaptability to agronomic practices, and suitability for mechanized harvesting [1; 3; 5; 7]. Since this trait has a polygenic nature, phenotypic variation within a population is closely associated with its genetic composition and environmental conditions. Therefore, in-depth investigation of the genetic system controlling plant height is crucial for organizing effective selection, identifying promising genotypes, and developing new high-yielding varieties [6; 13; 8; 12].

Assessing the inheritance and variability of plant height in Chinese–Uzbek cotton germplasm, particularly evaluating segregation processes in F_2 hybrid populations, provides an opportunity to identify transgressive forms in breeding programs. Such populations, due to their high genetic diversity, are rich sources of novel combinational genotypes and serve as essential material for selection. The present study, conducted under a 0:1:0 irrigation regime, aims to objectively evaluate plant height characteristics of cotton varieties, identify genetically stable and promising donors, and develop scientific foundations for creating highly productive and mechanization-friendly cultivars.

Materials and Methods. A total of 37 cotton samples of Chinese–Uzbek origin, including local varieties, foreign breeding lines, and F_2 hybrid populations, were used as the research material. The studied germplasm consisted of the following groups: Local breeding varieties: Genofond-2, Ravnaq-1, Ravnaq-2, Guliston, Namangan-77, Sulton, Andijon-35, C-6570, C-2616, C-5706, C-5707, C-8290, C-7301, C-6524, C-6580, and others. Chinese accessions: Xitoy-56, Xitoy-65, Xitoy-66, XLZ-78. Technological lines: T-205, T-206, T-209, T-210, T-215, T-216, T-220, T-223, T-224, T-228. F_2 hybrid populations: F_2 Porloq-4 \times Xitoy-65, F_2 C-8290 \times XLZ-78, F_2 Xitoy-44 \times C-6580, F_2 XLZ-78 \times C-6575.

Methods. The study was conducted under a 0:1:0 irrigation regime at the field experimental site of the CBSPARI “Cotton Biotechnology” Laboratory. This irrigation system provided conditions for accurately assessing vegetative growth, stress tolerance, and the phenotypic expression of hereditary factors in the plants. The obtained data were statistically processed and evaluated according to the methodology of B. Dospekhov (1985).

Results and Discussion. The inheritance, variability, and formation of the plant height (main stem height) trait in Chinese–Uzbek cotton germplasm samples were analyzed under a 0:1:0 irrigation regime. Table 1 presents the mathematical–statistical analyses of plant height in various cotton varieties and F_2 hybrid populations. These analyses made it possible to determine the average growth rate of each variety, the range of variability within populations, the genetic stability of the traits, and their breeding value.

Plant height is one of the key morphobiological traits in cotton breeding, as it directly affects several economically important characteristics such as vegetative growth vigor, the number of fruiting branches, yield level, lodging resistance, suitability for mechanization, and tolerance to environmental factors. Since this trait has a polygenic nature, its variation within a population is closely associated with the genetic structure and environmental conditions.

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the mean plant height (M) among the studied varieties ranged from 68 to 122 cm. Varieties and hybrids with an average height of 105–123 cm are classified as tall-growing populations with strong vegetative vigor. For example, C-7301, O'zPITI-203, F_2 Porloq-4 \times Xitoy-65, F_2 C-8290 \times XLZ-78, and F_2 XLZ-78 \times C-6575 exhibited very tall plant height, indicating a pronounced heterosis effect. Such genotypes carry genes associated with enhanced vegetative growth and therefore serve as important donors in developing tall, highly branched, and vegetatively vigorous hybrid cotton lines. The wide variation observed in plant height among the hybrid populations indicates that they are still undergoing segregation. This makes them highly valuable material for selection, as desirable and promising genotypes can be effectively identified and isolated during the breeding process.

Conversely, several varieties with mean plant heights of $M < 80$ cm were also identified in the table, including *Ravnaq-2*, *Niso*, *C-5706*, *C-5707*, *Xitoy-56*, *Xitoy-66*, and others. These are compact, short-statured populations that are advantageous for mechanized harvesting technologies and dense planting schemes. The presence of growth-restrictor genes is likely in these varieties.

The coefficient of variation (V%) reflects the stability of the trait. Varieties with a V% of 7–10 (such as *C-6570*, *Xitoy-66*, *XLZ-78*, *C-2616*, etc.) are genetically stable, showing uniform plant height within the population and reliable inheritance across generations. Such varieties are highly suitable as parental forms in breeding programs. Varieties with a V% of 10–14% exhibit moderate phenotypic variability, indicating populations that can be easily managed through selection. Varieties with $V\% > 15\%$ (including *Andijon-35*, *T-215* and certain F_2 hybrids) demonstrate high variability, reflecting a strong segregation process. These populations are particularly valuable because selection can be highly effective, allowing breeders to isolate promising phenotypes with high potential.

In most of the F_2 hybrid populations presented in Table 1, the mean plant height was considerably high, accompanied by wide variability, indicating the emergence of transgressive forms. In particular, the hybrid F_2 *XLZ-78* × *C-6575* demonstrated strong vegetative vigor. Such hybrids serve as valuable genetic resources for developing new cotton varieties characterized by tall stature, extensive branching, and high productivity.

Table 1.

Inheritance, variability, and formation of the plant height trait in Chinese-Uzbek cotton germplasm samples under a 0:1:0 irrigation regime.

№	Name of varieties, hybrids, and samples	n	K=10 (cm)						M, (cm)	m	δ	V%
			60-69,9	70-79,9	80-89,9	90-99,9	100-109,9	110-119,9				
1	Genofond-2	18		3	6		6	3	89,95	2,53	10,74	11,94
2	Ravnaq-1	18		3	6	3	4	2	92,73	3,49	14,79	15,95
3	O'zPITI-203	18		3	3	6	4	2	104,39	2,89	12,25	11,73
4	C-6570	18			1	10	6	1	98,84	1,83	7,76	7,85
5	Guliston	18		9	8	1			80,51	1,90	8,06	10,01
6	Niso	18	3	12	3				74,95	1,36	5,77	7,70
7	C-5710	19	3		10	4	2		87,58	2,03	8,86	10,12
8	Namangan-77	18		2	3	6	7		94,95	2,99	12,69	13,37
9	C-8290	18		12	3	3			79,95	2,13	9,05	11,32
10	C-7301	18		6	9	3			112,17	2,39	10,13	9,03
11	Andijon-35	18	1	2	4	5	6		92,17	4,06	17,22	18,68
12	Ravnaq-2	18	12	5	1				68,84	1,65	7,01	10,19
13	C-2616	18	3	12	3				74,95	1,36	5,77	7,70
14	C-5706	18	9	6	3				71,62	2,33	9,88	13,79
15	C-5707	19	10	6	3				71,27	2,21	9,62	13,51
16	C-6580	18	8	7	3				72,17	2,39	10,13	14,04
17	Sulton	18	3	7	6	2			78,84	2,28	9,67	12,27
18	C-6524	18	5	10	3				73,84	1,57	6,66	9,02

19	Xitoy-56	18	6	9	3				73,28	1,66	7,06	9,63
20	Xitoy-66	18	3	12	3				74,95	1,36	5,77	7,70
21	Xitoy-65	18	6	8	4				73,84	1,76	7,45	10,09
22	XLZ-78	18	2	12	4				76,06	1,36	5,77	7,58
23	T-205	18		6	8	4			92,17	2,39	10,13	10,99
24	T-206	18		6	10	2			82,73	1,57	6,65	8,03
25	T-209	18		4	7	4	3		88,28	2,48	10,51	11,91
26	T-210	18		1	8	7	2		90,51	2,20	9,34	10,32
27	T-215	18		8	5		3	2	84,39	3,24	13,77	16,31
28	T-211	18			10	5	3		91,06	2,27	9,61	10,55
29	T-216	18			4	8		6	96,06	1,76	7,45	7,75
30	T-220	18		10	4	4			81,62	2,05	8,68	10,63
31	T-223	18			5	10	3		93,84	1,57	6,66	7,10
32	T-224	18	6	9			3		73,28	1,66	7,06	9,63
33	T-228	17	2	3	9		2	1	93,19	2,42	9,99	10,72
34	F ₂ Porloq-4xXitoy-65	23			1		6	6	105,82	2,69	12,88	12,17
35	F ₂ C-8290xXLZ-78	12					2	3	109,12	2,72	9,43	8,64
36	F ₂ Xitoy-44xC-6580	15				1	3	3	106,95	3,22	12,48	11,67
37	F ₂ XLZ-78xC-6575	20			1	4	4	4	122,95	3,98	17,80	14,48

Overall, based on the data presented in the table, the varieties can be classified according to plant height as follows:

short-statured, stable varieties — suitable for developing new compact-type cultivars; medium-height, stable varieties — optimal as the main breeding pool due to their compatibility with mechanization and satisfactory yield potential; tall, vigorous-growing varieties — valuable donors carrying genes for strong vegetative growth; and F₂ populations with wide variability — representing the primary material for selection due to their high segregation and potential for identifying superior phenotypes.

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